

Drug Abuse and Criminal Behaviour among Youths in Rumuigbo Community, Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State

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Abstract

This article examines the relationship between drug abuse and criminal behaviour among youths in Rumuigbo community in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Guided mainly by Sutherland's differential association theory, the study draws on a community-based survey of 300 respondents from both the youth and three family groups, supported by interviews and observations. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using simple frequencies, percentages, and chi-square tests. The findings show that most respondents believe that youths who abuse drugs are more likely to engage in criminal acts, that drug abuse harms the body, and that an increase in the number of drug abusers intensifies negative effects on the community. Respondents also feel that inadequate funding limits the effectiveness of drug law enforcement agencies. The chi-square result indicates a significant association between family group membership and patterns of response, which supports the idea that intimate social networks play a key role in the learning of both drug use and criminal behaviour. The article concludes that drug abuse among youths in the Rumuigbo community is best understood as a learned behaviour that grows within peer and family networks, and thus recommends family-based prevention, stronger community structures, and improved support for enforcement and rehabilitation services.

Keywords: *Drug abuse, Criminal behaviour, Youth, Differential association, public health, Rumuigbo.*

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Introduction

Drug abuse is now recognised as one of the major social and public health challenges facing Nigerian communities. A drug can be understood as any substance, other than food, that affects the structure or function of a living organism when it enters the body. Used correctly, drugs relieve pain and cure disease. When misused, they harm the body, cloud judgment, and disrupt social life (Peters, 2015). In Nigeria, young people are especially exposed

to cannabis, prescription drugs used without medical supervision, volatile solvents, and locally prepared mixtures. Drug abuse among youths is closely linked with school dropout, cultism, interpersonal violence, and involvement in theft and armed robbery. Wider structural factors such as unemployment and uneven development create fertile ground for these problems to grow (Reilly & Witt (1992, Ake, 2001; FMoH, 2019; Real et al 2021).

While Orukwogu et al (2023) defined a drug as any substance that, when introduced into the

body, alters the normal biological and psychological functioning of the body, especially the central nervous system. On the other hand, drug abuse is the overindulgence in and dependence on a drug or other chemicals that are detrimental to the individual's physical and mental health or the welfare of others (Gebissa, 2010). Studies have repeatedly confirmed that drug abuse occurs at all economic levels of society, from the wealthy to the impoverished, and among young people as well as adults in Nigeria, like many countries of the world. In the same vein, adolescents who leave school prematurely are at an increased risk of substance abuse, revealing a pattern of substance abuse in out-of-school adolescents (Obi et al, 2024).

Several scholars have asserted that drug abuse is a multi-factorial problem influenced by socio-economic conditions and a lack of awareness about the health impacts of substance use (Reichert et al 2021, Himanshu & Sandeep, 2024) on one hand, and a social epidemic linked to family dysfunction and peer pressure among adolescents (Grant & Enyindah, 2024). For Chime & Walter (2025) and Ompad & Fuller (2025), they consider drug abuse as a significant public health issue exacerbated by urbanization and poverty, while also becoming more common among young people living in low-income countries with challenging circumstances, such as those on the streets (Real et al., 2021; World Health Organization, 2022). They advocate for integrated intervention strategies combining public health and law enforcement.

Adetiloye & Abel (2022) in their study on Drug Abuse Among Nigerian Youth and Its Consequences noted how the youth use drugs illegally and unlawfully till it becomes harmful to them, that the Nigerian youths are deliberately using drugs illegally, unlawfully, and intentionally, while many are ignorantly or knowingly depending on one drug or the other for their daily activities. In Nigeria's South-South Geopolitical Zone, which has a population of 12,763,644 people aged 15 to 64. According to United Nations statistics from 2019, the prevalence of various substances in this region is increasingly becoming worrisome, with over 16.6 % engaged in drug usage, accounting for an astonishing 2124,000 people (Oritsemuelebi et al

2025). Evidence shows that Drug trafficking in Nigeria is intricately linked to organized crime, with criminal syndicates controlling a significant portion of the illicit drug trade (NDLEA, 2020). This identifies drug abuse as a challenge to national security due to its link with organized crime and terrorism, thereby calling for a multi-agency approach to address the menace (Obot, 2013, and Fajemirokun, 2024).

In a survey by the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA, 2011, Fatima, 2017), results on drug use and abuse data from schools, records of patients admitted at mental health institutions for drug problems, and interview of persons arrested for drug offenses revealed that youths constitute the high-risk group for drug abuse, with over 90% of sampled respondents. Similarly in India as in several part of the world, drug threat has become of increasing concern to public health with a report indicating that 1 in every 18 persons under 15-64 years age group have used drug in a year between 2010-2020, but had increased to 26% from the earlier years (UNODC, 2013, 2022, Himanshu & Sandeep, 2024).

In Rivers state according to Ogunka et al (2020) and Grant & Enyindah (2024), there are issues of violence, rape, kidnapping, arm robbery and many other several vices, and these nefarious activities are attributed to drug abuse, as they frequently consumed drugs to "get high" with complete disregard to medical expert advice thus resulting in ill-behaviour and undesirable consequences. In specific terms, the findings of Grant & Enyindah (2024) in their study on Drug Abuse Among Youths in Rivers State, 2015-2020, indicate that areas like Ogoni, Ahoada, Etche, Port Harcourt, and Obio Akpor are the hotspots for drug abuse in Rivers State. These places were also found to correlate with the areas that are prone to violence and criminality, just as the available Crime records on Rivers State indicate these places as having the highest criminal index in the state (RSMoH, 2019, 2020; Ogunka et al 2020).

Generally, there have been ongoing deliberate efforts to reduce drug circulation and consumption, especially among Nigeria's youth, and this has informed several policies and laws

in Nigeria. In 1984, President Muhammadu Buhari introduced a decree imposing strict penalties on drug traffickers and users, but this failed to deter either group. Under President Gbadamosi Babangida, the decree was repealed, leading to the establishment of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA, 1992, 2011). In January 1992, a national conference at the National Institute of Policy and Strategic Studies highlighted key issues regarding drug abuse, including its roots in societal corruption and the pursuit of material wealth. Nigeria's role has shifted from being merely a transit country to a significant drug-consuming nation. (NDLEA, 2020, Oritsemuelebi et al. 2025). These initiatives reflect the government's ongoing concerns about drug abuse and control in Nigeria, yet they have not been as effective as anticipated, hence the justification for this study.

Rumuigbo, a community in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, is not exempt and formed the sampled location and setting for this Study. Residents report rising numbers of youths who are out of school, unemployed, and often under the influence of drugs (NDLEA, 2021). Families speak of sons who become unmanageable, while elders compare the present situation with earlier years when traditional structures imposed discipline more firmly (Peters, 2015; Adebayo & Ogunleye, 2022). Rumuigbo is part of the Ekinigbo clan in Apará Kingdom in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. In the past, traditional institutions such as youth councils, women's groups, and elders' councils enforced discipline and settled disputes. Over time, modern pressures, disputes over traditional leadership, and exposure to urban life have changed social control patterns. Many residents now report visible drug use by youths and a rise in criminal activity (Alagoa, 1985).

Although drug abuse and youth crime are often discussed in public forums, there has been limited empirical work that focuses on Rumuigbo itself. The project on which this article is based sought to fill that gap. The specific objectives were to:

1. examine whether drug abuse is perceived as harmful to the body.
2. determine whether criminal behaviour among youths in Rumuigbo community is associated with drug abuse.
3. assess whether inadequate funding is perceived as a barrier to drug law enforcement.
4. identify perceived effects of drug abuse on the wider community.
5. From these objectives, the following questions were posed. These include:
6. To what extent is drug abuse perceived as harmful to the body?
7. How are youths who abuse drugs more likely to engage in criminal behaviour?
8. What role does inadequate funding play in weakening the work of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA)?
9. How do people in the Rumuigbo community perceive the effects of drug abuse and youth crime on their community?

Furthermore, it was hypothesized that youths who abuse drugs have a higher tendency to engage in criminal behaviour, while an increase in the number of drug abusers leads to a greater negative impact on society.

Theoretical and Empirical Background

Differential Association Theory

This study is anchored in Edwin Sutherland's differential association theory, which views criminal behaviour as something that is learned in social interaction rather than inherited. Sutherland (1947) argued that individuals learn techniques of committing crime as well as the motives, rationalisations, and attitudes that support such acts. Learning takes place in intimate personal groups where people share time and conversation. A person becomes delinquent when the balance of definitions that favour law violation outweighs those that oppose it in terms of frequency, duration, priority, and intensity (Sutherland, 1947; Iwarimie-Jaja, 1995).

Applied to drug abuse, the theory suggests that youths are introduced to substances such as cannabis or other psychoactive drugs by friends, cult companions, and other close contacts. They learn where to buy drugs, how to use them, how to avoid detection by parents and police, and how to justify their habits. As interaction with these groups grows stronger, the likelihood of continued drug use and involvement in crime also grows (Peters, 2015; Adelowokan et al, 2019; Umar & David, 2019).

Drug Abuse and Its Consequences

Drug abuse refers to the use of legal or illegal drugs in a way that is harmful, excessive, or outside medical supervision. It may involve illicit substances or the misuse of prescription medicines (Baker, 2012). The Rumuigbo project report lists abused drugs under several broad classes, including cannabinoids, depressants, hallucinogens, opioids, stimulants, inhalants, and anabolic steroids, each with specific routes of administration and effects on the body (Peters, 2015; Houston, 2023). The health consequences range from acute poisoning to long-term cardiovascular disease, liver and kidney damage, respiratory problems, mental illness, and, in some cases, death. Pregnant women who abuse drugs are at risk of miscarriage, premature delivery, and low birth weight. Sharing contaminated needles increases the spread of blood-borne infections. At the social level, drug abuse contributes to family conflict, child neglect, school failure, job loss, and community unrest (Peters, 2015).

Drug Abuse, Unemployment, and Crime

Many studies have explored links between unemployment, social inequality, and crime. While Box (1985) examined the impact of recession on crime in the United Kingdom and found that economic stress can increase both property crime and public anxiety, Reilly and Witt (1992) reported a strong relationship between unemployment and crime in Scotland, using an econometric analysis of regional data, just as the same context has been reported in Nigeria by several scholars. For instance, in Nigeria, structural pressures are reflected in youth unemployment, weakened family structures, and limited opportunities for

education and advancement. Within this context, drug abuse can function as a coping mechanism, a marker of status among peers, and a pathway into crime and gang activity (Peters, 2015).

Ebobob & Akujobi (2022), in their study, revealed that there is a strong bi-directional link between unemployment, poverty and crime in Nigeria, and contended that since poverty negatively affects unemployment and crime rates,, thus the rate of unemployment, if reduced through provision of jobs will consequently reduce the rate of poverty and also make crime unattractive on the long run. In the same vein, Adelowokan et al. (2019),Umar & David (2019), and Adebobola et al. (2015) have also found that an increase in unemployment causes an increase in poverty level in Nigeria, a critical factor that leads to an increased crime rate and affects economic development.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design on the premise that this design is appropriate when the aim is to describe existing conditions and relationships among variables without manipulating them (Osuala, 2001). Questionnaires were used to gather quantitative data, while interviews and observation provided qualitative insight and helped to cross check responses.

The target population comprised youths and key family representatives in Rumuigbo. For practical reasons, the study focused on three large family groups: Walison, Wodo, and Okocha. Within each group, respondents were selected by simple random sampling. In all, a total of 300 respondents participated in the survey, which is made up of youth and family groups, and using a set of structured questionnaires administered and interviews sessions to elicit information from the respondents.

In specific terms, a total of 40 copies of structured questionnaires were administered among the youth groups, while the three purposively selected family groups form the remaining 260 respondents. The main instrument was a structured questionnaire made

up of two sections. Section A collected demographic information such as age, sex, education, occupation, and religion. Section B contained questions on: how youths learn to use drugs; whether youths who abuse drugs are more likely to engage in criminal behaviour; perceived harms of drug abuse to the individual; perceived effects of drug abuse on society; and perceived challenges facing drug law enforcement agencies

Most items in Section B were closed-ended, with Yes or No response options. Open-ended questions and interviews with chiefs, family heads, and mothers were used to deepen understanding and to explain patterns noted in the quantitative data. Responses were edited, coded, and summarised in frequency tables. Percentages were calculated to show the distribution of answers. For hypothesis testing, the chi-square statistic was applied to selected questions to compare observed and expected frequencies across family groups.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of the Youth Group respondents.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	24	60
	Female	16	40
Education (summary)	Educated	40	100
Religion	Christian	40	100

Source: Field Survey (2025)

All respondents had some formal education and identified as Christian. The sample was slightly more male than female. These patterns reflect the general composition of active youth and family representatives in the community.

Perceived Link between Drug Abuse and Criminal Behaviour

A central question asked whether youths who abuse drugs are more likely to engage in criminal behaviour.

Table 3. Perception that Youths Who Abuse Drugs Engage in Criminal Behaviour

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	30	75
No	10	25
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Three quarters of the respondents agreed that youths who abuse drugs are more likely to commit crimes. Only one quarter disagreed.

Perceived Harm of Drug Abuse to the Body

Respondents were asked whether they think drug abuse is harmful to the individual.

Table 4. Perception that Drug Abuse Harms the Body

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	34	85
No	6	15
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey (2025)

A large majority, 85 percent, agreed that drug abuse harms the body. Only 15 percent felt otherwise. In interviews, respondents mentioned “madness”, physical weakness, and death as possible outcomes of drug use.

Perceived Effect of Drug Abuse on Society

The study also considered whether people believe that as the number of drug abusers increases, the effect on society increases.

Table 5. Perception that an Increase in Drug Abuse Leads to Greater Social Harm

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	32	80
No	8	20
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Four out of five respondents agreed that more drug abusers mean more problems for the

community. They linked this to theft, violence, and insecurity in their neighbourhood.

Perceived Effect of Funding and Training on Law Enforcement

Finally, respondents were asked whether adequate funding and training encourage agencies responsible for fighting drugs and crime to perform better.

Table 6. Perception that Adequate Funding and Training Improve Drug Law Enforcement

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	36	90
No	4	10
Total	40	100

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Most respondents believed that better funding and training would strengthen the work of NDLEA and other relevant agencies.

Hypothesis Testing

To explore how family group membership relates to attitudes, responses were grouped into “Agree”, “Disagree”, and “Indifferent” categories and cross tabulated with the three family groups. The resulting contingency table contained nine cells with a total frequency of 260.

The chi square statistic was computed with the usual formula

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e} \quad (1)$$

Questionnaire Survey and Response by Family Groups

Table 7 shows how questionnaires were distributed across the three family groups and the frequency of their response.

Table 7. Survey among the Three Selected Family Groups and Their Response

Family group	Agree	Disagree	Indifferent	Row total	Percentage
Walison family group	50	15	20	85	32.7
Wodo family group	60	25	10	95	36.5
Okocha family group	55	18	7	80	30.8
Column total	165	58	37	260	100

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 8. Chi-Square Calculation for Association between Family Group and Response Category

Cell	f _o	f _e	f _o - f _e	(f _o - f _e) ²	(f _o - f _e) ² / f _e
1	50	53.94	-3.94	15.52	0.29
2	15	18.96	-3.96	15.68	0.83
3	20	12.09	+7.91	62.57	5.18
4	60	60.29	-0.29	0.08	0.00
5	25	21.19	+3.81	14.52	0.69
6	10	13.52	-3.52	12.39	0.92
7	55	50.77	+4.23	17.89	0.35
8	18	17.85	+0.15	0.02	0.00
9	7	11.38	-4.38	19.18	1.69
					χ² ≈ 9.93

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Note: Cells 1–3 = Walison (Agree, Disagree, Indifferent); 4–6 = Wodo; 7–9 = Okocha. With 4 degrees of freedom, $\chi^2 \approx 9.93$ exceeds the critical value at the 0.05 level, so the null hypothesis of no association is rejected.

The calculated value was about 9.93 with 4 degrees of freedom. At the 5 percent level, this value is higher than the critical table value, so the null hypothesis of no difference was rejected. In plain terms, there is a significant association between family group membership and patterns of response to questions on drug abuse and criminal behaviour.

Discussion of Findings

Generally, the findings from Rumuigbo Community are consistent with differential association theory and with wider research on youth, unemployment, and crime. Three-quarters of respondents believe that youths who abuse drugs are more likely to engage in crime. This supports the idea that when young people spend time with peers who normalise drug use and law-breaking, they are more likely to adopt both the practices and the justifications of that group (Sutherland, 1947; Iwarimie-Jaja, 1995). The strong majority view that drug abuse harms the body also indicates that ignorance is not the root of the problem. People in Rumuigbo understand the health risks. Yet young people may still use drugs as a way to feel confident, to cope with stress, to follow friends, or to escape boredom and frustration in a difficult economic environment (Ake, 2001; Peters, 2015).

Respondents are clear that as the number of drug abusers rises, the community experiences more theft, assault, and general disorder. This mirrors findings in other settings where economic hardship and weak social control combine to increase crime (Box, 1985; Reilly & Witt, 1992). In Rumuigbo, elders describe how drug-related behaviour has undermined respect for traditional authority and disturbed family life. The perception that NDLEA and similar agencies lack adequate funding speaks to the institutional side of the problem. Where residents see open drug selling and only occasional arrests, confidence in law enforcement may fall. Dealers can act more boldly when they feel that agencies do not have enough resources or support from higher authorities.

The chi-square result, which shows significant differences across family groups, is important as it suggests that intimate social networks within certain lineages shape how people view drug abuse and crime. Some families may have strong internal controls and clear messages against drugs. Others may be more exposed to the drug trade or may tolerate it for economic reasons. Differential association theory helps us see how these patterns of contact and communication within families and peer groups shape actual behaviour. Overall, the evidence portrays drug abuse among youths in the Rumuigbo community as a learned social practice that grows within networks under stress. It is not simply a matter of individual weakness. Structural conditions, family dynamics, and peer influence all contribute to the problem.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study presents a concise account of drug abuse and criminal behaviour among youths in Rumuigbo Community in Obio Akpor LGA of Rivers State. Using a descriptive survey of 300 respondents and basic statistical analysis, supported by interviews and observation, the study has shown that;

1. Drug abuse is widely recognised as harmful to the body.
2. Most respondents believe that youths who abuse drugs are more likely to engage in criminal behaviour.
3. Increases in the number of drug abusers are seen as drivers of community-level insecurity.
4. People feel that inadequate funding limits the effectiveness of drug law enforcement agencies.
5. Family group membership is associated with differing patterns of response, which supports the importance of intimate social networks.

Addressing drug abuse among youths in Rumuigbo thus requires action from families, community leaders, law enforcement agencies, schools, and faith-based bodies. The findings of this study give a grounded basis for such action and highlight the need to see drug abuse as a

social process that can be prevented and redirected.

In line with these conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested.

1. *Strengthen family-based prevention.* Parents and guardians should receive guidance on how to observe behavioural changes, talk openly about drugs, and set clear limits. Community meetings and church programmes can provide simple materials and workshops for this purpose.
2. *Revive and support community structures.* Youth councils, women's groups, and elders' councils can be encouraged to monitor known drug spots, organise positive activities for young people, and support families that are struggling with drug-related problems.
3. *Improve funding and training for enforcement and rehabilitation.* The government should increase funding for NDLEA and related agencies, and also invest in counselling and rehabilitation centres where youths can receive treatment, learn skills, and reintegrate into the community.
4. *Use schools and faith-based organisations for early education.* Schools and churches in Rumuigbo can introduce age-appropriate lessons on drugs, self-control, and non-violent ways of dealing with frustration.
5. *Promote further community-level research.* Future studies could involve larger samples, cover more neighbourhoods, and apply more advanced statistical techniques. Qualitative studies focusing on the life histories of drug-using youths would also add depth.
6. *Strengthening of the drug law enforcement agency.* There is a need to strengthen the drug law enforcement agency in their effort to combat illicit drug sales and misuse in every part of the state and in particular the study area, to ensure that the laws guiding drug abuse are strictly executed by relevant government agencies like NDLEA and offenders duly prosecuted.
7. *A comprehensive, collaborative, and more inclusive approach to campaigns.* There is a need for a comprehensive, collaborative, and more inclusive approach to campaigns against drug abuse by the government and other stakeholders.

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